

AN ONSET THEORY FOR IRREVERSIBLE DEFORMATION IN COMPOSITE MATERIALS

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ABSTRACT

It is timely to re-examine the onset of the irreversible deformation of composite materials. In this paper we examine the behavior of off-axis tensile specimens of unidirectional tape laminates. We do so utilizing the simulation tools and physics-based onset criteria that advances in computing power have made possible since the first studies were made. Simulation tools utilize the finite-element method wherein the states of microscopic deformation within the discrete continuum phases, fiber and matrix, can be completely and thoroughly analyzed. Here the properties and performance characteristics of the fiber and matrix are reflected in appropriate constitutive relationships and the representative volume element is constrained to effectively reflect the micro-structural geometry.

Dehomogenization

Onset of irreversible deformation in composite materials that begins in the matrix phase can be predicted only when the deformation state within that phase of the heterogeneous composite has been determined as a function of the multi-axial deformation in the homogenized medium making up the complex geometry of the composite structure. The challenge is to link the deformations at the macroscopic structural level to the microscopic deformations of the matrix phase and to do so in a computationally efficient manner. While possible, simple extension of mesh refinement processes is not an efficient manner to achieve this objective. In the following, the authors describe a process to achieve dehomogenization of a composite structure in an efficient manner that allows determination of the components of the strain tensor field within the matrix phase that allows for consideration of the geometric complexity and heterogeneity of the microstructure.

Consider the following diagram of the homogenization process in modeling of composite structure consisting of continuous and collimated fibers suspended in a continuous matrix phase shown in Figure 1. The first step is to replace the heterogeneous composite material with an equivalent homogeneous medium. Micromechanical models have been developed to accomplish this step using various volume averaging approaches. This provides the engineering elastic properties of the lamina, the building block of the multi-axial laminate. Next the laminate is constructed consisting of laminae with prescribed fiber directions with respect to the laminate principal direction and the effective laminate properties are determined with laminated plate or shell theory. The composite structural model is then developed by combining laminate properties with joints and structural geometry, typically with finite element models. Finally, the structural response is determined by subjecting the structural model to external loads and environment.

Homogenization in Modeling Composite Structure

Figure 1

Dehomogenization begins with the model of a homogenized structural model as shown in Figure 2. The initial conditions for the problem are the structural response of the homogenized composite structural model when subjected to external loads and environment. Geometric discontinuities, joints and geometry are considered to yield local deformation states within the laminate. Next, laminate analysis is utilized to determine deformation states within the individual lamina. Finally, micromechanical models are engaged to determine deformation in the fiber and matrix phases. While the process described is straight forward in concept, its execution relies upon the development of efficient and high fidelity methods to accomplish each step in the dehomogenization step. Simple mesh refinement cannot achieve the required efficiency at all levels, especially at the microscopic level wherein the deformations fields exhibit great variations. In the present study, the authors summarize the method of $\tilde{\text{micromechanical enhancement}}$ developed earlier for this purpose. Next, structural analysis is illustrated for the off-axis tensile coupon as an example of the approach. Strain invariants are determined within the matrix phase of a conventional carbon fiber/epoxy composite and utilized to determine the onset of irreversible deformation. These predictions are compared to strength results for several off-axis angles.

Dehomogenization in Modeling Fiber and Matrix Deformations

Figure 2

Micromechanical Analysis

Micromechanical analysis for dehomogenization is the inverse to the method when used for homogenization. The strains in the lamina are amplified in the representative volume element so that the individual constituent strains, reflecting both the heterogeneity of the microstructure and the lamina deformations, can be determined. In an earlier work [1], the authors presented an efficient approach to the micromechanical analysis utilizing the influence function method.

In the following we describe one such step toward computational efficiency first reported in [1] wherein the magnitudes of fiber and matrix strain tensors within representative volume element are determined from arbitrary states of strain of the lamina. The relationship between fiber and matrix responses and arbitrary lamina strains is cast as an influence function formulation wherein the canonical states of strain in the representative volume element (RVE) are related to the state of strain at specified geometric points within the unit cell. The specific points can be chosen to anticipate geometric regions of greatest interest. Further, the true geometric order at the microscopic level can be taken as represented by RVE of hexagonal and square array geometries (Figure 1) and this approach can be carried out for both microstructural geometries. Estimates of the influence of variations in microstructural geometry can be incorporated into the analyses by utilizing results from the two unit cell geometries.

To determine the terms within the influence function matrix, it is necessary to carry out full three-dimensional finite-element analyses of the microstructural representative volume

element (Figure 2) subjected to the six canonical states of strain wherein the unit cell deformation corresponds to a single component of strain. Further, free thermal strain of the RVE provides microstructural thermal strains. While these calculations are tedious and computationally intense, they only need be carried out once for a given microstructural geometry.

Consider the representative volume element subjected to an arbitrary state of strain, $\bar{\varepsilon}_j - \bar{\alpha}_j \Delta T$, (j=1-6) including both thermal and mechanical components with $\bar{\alpha}_j$ the effective coefficient of thermal expansion of the homogenized medium. The state of strain at a prescribed point within the representative volume element can be determined from the following relationship:

$$\varepsilon_i^k - \alpha_i^k \Delta T = M_{ij}^k (\bar{\varepsilon}_j - \bar{\alpha}_j \Delta T) + A_i^k \Delta T \quad (i, j = 1 - 6) \quad (1)$$

Where M_{ij}^k is the influence function matrix at the kth point in the RVE and A_i^k is the thermal vector of strain, per unit thermal change, induced at the point of interest within the boundaries of the unconstrained representative volume element. This formulation was first developed by Gosse [1] and has been extended by Yudhanto [2], Tay et al [3] and Ha et al [4]. Ha et al [4] extended the method to include a stress formulation and examined microstructural stress distributions due to traction boundary conditions, but failed to cite the original work of Gosse [1].

The components of the influence function matrix can easily be determined uniquely by prescribing a canonical state of deformation of the representative volume element and carrying out three-dimensional finite element analyses within the representative volume element to determine the components of the strain tensor at the specified point, k. For example, let $\bar{\varepsilon}_j=0$, (j=2-6) and $\bar{\varepsilon}_1=1$ and $\Delta T=0$, then,

$$\begin{aligned} \varepsilon_1^k &= M_{11}^k \bar{\varepsilon}_1 \text{ or } M_{11}^k = \varepsilon_1^k \\ \varepsilon_2^k &= M_{21}^k \bar{\varepsilon}_1 \text{ or } M_{21}^k = \varepsilon_2^k \\ \varepsilon_3^k &= M_{31}^k \bar{\varepsilon}_1 \text{ or } M_{31}^k = \varepsilon_3^k \\ \varepsilon_4^k &= M_{41}^k \bar{\varepsilon}_1 \text{ or } M_{41}^k = \varepsilon_4^k \\ \varepsilon_5^k &= M_{51}^k \bar{\varepsilon}_1 \text{ or } M_{51}^k = \varepsilon_5^k \\ \varepsilon_6^k &= M_{61}^k \bar{\varepsilon}_1 \text{ or } M_{61}^k = \varepsilon_6^k \end{aligned} \quad (2)$$

Note that for any point, k, a single finite-element analysis with boundary conditions appropriate to the condition, $\bar{\varepsilon}_1=1$ yields six of the 36 coefficients in the influence function matrix. Five more finite-element analyses are required to determine the remaining terms of M_{ij}^k . However, these same six finite-element analyses can produce the terms of M_{ij}^k at another point, k within the medium as well. Thus, only six finite-element models need to be constructed for a given representative volume element geometry to determine any number of influence function matrices. This clarifies why it is necessary to choose *a priori* specific points within the medium where the components of the strain tensor are to be determined. While this restriction may appear to limit the utility of this approach, careful study of the strain distributions within the heterogeneous medium suggest several points where the greatest magnitude in the selected measure of the strain field can be expected to occur. For the matrix phase, the points chosen differ for the two representative volume elements. For

the square array, three points within the matrix phase are chosen as shown in Figure 3. These points represent both the point the greatest distance from the fiber phase and the two points where the fibers are closest to one another. For the hexagonal array again the point where the least distance between fibers occurs is chosen along with two other intermediate points. It should be noted that all points of interrogation for the square array lie on the surface of the RVE, while two of the interrogation points for the hexagonal array fall within the RVE and one lies on the surface.

Figure 1: Interrogation locations within the Matrix Phase for Hexagonal and Square Arrays

Equation (1) demands that the RVE exhibit the free thermal deformation $\bar{\alpha}_j \Delta T$ ($j = 1-3$) in order that the homogenized mechanical strains vanish. In this case, the unit cell free thermal deformation is equal to that defined by the coefficients of thermal expansion of the homogenized unidirectional lamina, $\bar{\alpha}_j \Delta T$.

$$\begin{aligned} \varepsilon_i^k - \alpha_i^k \Delta T &= M_{ij}^k (\bar{\varepsilon}_j - \bar{\alpha}_j \Delta T) + A_i^k \Delta T \quad (i, j = 1-6) \\ \text{Let } \bar{\varepsilon}_j &= \bar{\alpha}_j \Delta T \quad (j = 1-3) \end{aligned} \quad (3)$$

The thermal strain enhancement vector is identically defined as:

$$A_i^k = \frac{\varepsilon_i^k - \alpha_i^k \Delta T}{\Delta T} \quad (i = 1-6) \quad (4)$$

Finite Element Analysis

Modeling the response of the off-axis tensile test presents several challenges as discussed in reference [6]. Stress concentrations are often induced in highly anisotropic structures by boundary conditions. This is certainly the case for the off-axis tests where the fiber orientation angle is in the range 1 to 25 degrees, as will be discussed in detail later. With displacement boundary conditions utilized to introduce load into the specimen, stress concentrations can occur at the intersection of planes where in boundary displacements are specified and the lateral specimen edges. These numerical events can distort stress and deformation predictions in the regions of the specimen wherein the onset of irreversible behavior may be expected to occur. Further, determination of the location of the site of the onset of irreversible behavior within the specimen geometry can be a challenge. This is true because there are a large number of locations that must be interrogated within the deformation fields of the test geometry and microstructure. Further, the development of

finite-element simulations for the off-axis tensile test geometry involves the establishment of boundary conditions that reflect the actual test conditions. Yet the complete modeling of the gripping systems can be unsatisfactory due to the need for simulation of load transfer between frictional grips and the test specimen. Therefore, the authors chose to model only the test section and to introduce the loading through boundary nodal displacements.

Consider the test specimen geometry of a rectangular parallelepiped of length, L width, W and thickness, T and displacement components u , v , w in the x , y , z directions. While the overall specimen length was 254 mm, the test section length, L for all test specimens was 152.4 mm while the nominal cross-sectional dimensions, W and T were 19.05 mm and 4.89 mm, respectively. While the lateral faces of the specimens: $(x,0,z)$, (x,W,z) , $(x,y,0)$ and (x,y,T) are taken as traction free, the loading boundary conditions are given in Table 3.

Table 3 Nodal displacement boundary conditions

Nodal Position (x,y,z)	Boundary Condition
0, 0, 0	$u = 0, v = 0, w = 0$
0, W, 0	$w = 0$
L, W, 0	$w = 0$
L, 0, 0	$w = 0$

Where the nodal displacement is not specified, the corresponding zero force condition is implied. The displacement of the nodes in the planes $(x = 0, L)$ are $u = 0$ at $x = 0$ and $u = \epsilon L$ at $x = L$ while the lateral displacements, v and w , of those nodes are unconstrained. For the prescription of displacements of boundary nodes along the lines $(L,y,0)$, (L,y,T) , $(L,0,z)$ and (L,W,z) , $v = 0$ is imposed to reflect lateral grip restraint. For nodes in the plane $x = 0$, $u = 0$ and for the plane, $x = L$, $u = \epsilon L$, where ϵ is the applied axial strain at failure.

Typical results for the strain tensor field within test section are shown in Figure 4a where significant strain gradients can be seen. Of particular importance are the strain concentrations at the specimen corners $(L,0,z)$ and $(0,W,z)$. It is important that the strain concentrations introduced by the specification of boundary conditions, that do not accurately reflect the actual behavior in that region, be eliminated from consideration when searching for the geometric point wherein the onset of irreversible deformation occurs. In the case of the off-axis coupon, the initiation site is also the site of the specimen fracture since onset and failure propagation are coincident. Recent experimental results for the full field determination of the deformation of the off-axis coupon also indicate that the observed strain tensor field, for the identical geometry specimen and material system to those tested in the present work, does not show the predicted strain concentration at these two points. Rather, the maximum axial strain is shown in Figure 4b to occur at the positions $(A,0,z)$ and (B,W,z) where the values of A_1 and A_2 for the 10 degree test specimen were: 25.3 mm and 126.5 mm, respectively.

a

b

Figure 4 (a) – FEA results for axial displacement in 10° specimen at failure strain; (b) visualization of strain field

In the present study, the authors have followed a specific procedure designed to determine the site of the onset of irreversible deformation that eliminates the positions of false strain concentration induced by the approximate boundary conditions. Two positions are identified for interrogation. The first is the intersection of a line with the specimen edge that is parallel to the fiber direction and passes through the geometric center of the specimen. Moving from that point along the specimen edges $(x,0,z)$ and (x,W,z) toward the specimen grip locations $(x = 0$ and $x = L)$, a convergence study is carried out for the magnitude of the strain components at each node until a the node is identified where the strain solution does not converge for the meshes utilized. The previous node is then chosen as the second point for interrogation. In each case the actual sites of the failure in the test specimens were examined to determine if they were located between the two afore mentioned interrogation sites. If this was the case, the experimental data was judged appropriate for further examination. The locations determined in the finite element analysis for the two interrogation sites for each of the test specimens are given in Table 4 where $x = A_1$ is the intersection site described earlier and $x = A_2$ the nodal position nearest the grip where convergence is assured.

Table 4. Interrogation point locations Intercept $x = A_1$, Convergence Pt. A_2 , $y = 0$

Angle , degrees	A_1 (Intercept Pt.), mm	A_2 (Convergence Pt.), mm
10	130.22	140.82
15	111.76	130.66
20	102.36	144.78
25	96.63	141.04
30	92.70	141.98
45	85.72	140.97
67	80.24	140.06
90	76.20	76.20

The values of the strain invariants are for dilatation:

$$J_1 = \varepsilon_1 + \varepsilon_2 + \varepsilon_3 \tag{X}$$

(written in terms of the principal strains) describes the dilatational component of the deformation, while the J_2 invariant defined by

$$J_2' = \sqrt{\frac{1}{6} \left[(\varepsilon_1 - \varepsilon_2)^2 + (\varepsilon_1 - \varepsilon_3)^2 + (\varepsilon_2 - \varepsilon_3)^2 \right]} \quad (Y)$$

describes the distortional component of deformation.

Results for the deviator strain invariant J_2' and the dilatational strain invariant, J_1 at failure were calculated within the matrix phase, utilizing the micromechanical strain enhancement procedure described in reference [5], for the two points interrogated and are shown in Tables 1 and 2.

Table 1 Deviatoric Strain Invariant, J_2'

Angle	Axial Strain	J_2' Conv. Pt.	J_2' Intercept Pt.	Average
10	0.0099	0.1207	0.1080	0.1144
15	0.0120	0.1206	0.1044	0.1125
20	0.0148	0.1346	0.0982	0.1164
25	0.0141	0.1000	0.0768	0.0884
30	0.0132	0.0769	0.0599	0.0684
45	0.0126	0.0436	0.0373	0.0405
67	0.0103	0.0260	0.0255	0.0258
90	0.0101	0.0264	0.0264	0.0264

Table 2 Dilatational Strain Invariant, J_1

Angle	Axial Strain	J_1 Conv. Pt.	J_1 Intercept Pt.	Average
10	0.0099	0.0154	0.0145	0.0149
15	0.0120	0.0199	0.0179	0.0189
20	0.0148	0.0277	0.0206	0.0242
25	0.0141	0.0271	0.0213	0.0242
30	0.0132	0.0259	0.0207	0.0233
45	0.0126	0.0255	0.0221	0.0238
67	0.0103	0.0231	0.0220	0.0226
90	0.0101	0.0240	0.0240	0.0240

The data presented in Tables 5 and 6 are shown for each of the test specimen off-axis angles in Figure 5. The significance of the form of the data presentation is that it shows that there exist two independent predictors of the onset of irreversible deformation within the polymeric phase of the composite material. The deviatoric strain invariant of 0.114 is seen to determine onset for off-axis angles 10, 15 and 20 degrees, while the dilatational invariant of 0.0237 determines onset of irreversible behavior for angles 25, 30, 45, 67 and 90 degrees. It should be pointed out that for angle of 20 degrees the two critical measures are near coincident. This measured occurrence is a coincidence, but it is consistent with the condition that at the off-

axis angle of 20 degrees one measure (J_1) ceases to be dominant while the second measure (J_2') takes on that role as the off-axis angle is increased.

Figure 5 J_1 versus J_2'

Conclusions

The onset of irreversible deformation in the polymeric matrix of an off-axis tensile test for a carbon fiber composite was examined by first determining the appropriateness of utilizing the strain invariants as measures of onset. Further, the key conclusion in this work is that the onset of irreversible deformation in glassy polymers is given by a surface in the space of *strain invariants* J_1 and J_2' . Results of linear finite-element analyses of the off-axis test specimen subjected to a uniform axial strain at the grips were presented that demonstrate the localization of the failure site in a region bounded by two points: i) the intersection of a line in the x-y plane, passing through the geometric center of the specimen, and the free edge and ii) a point removed from the boundary condition nodes wherein the strain tensor converges through mesh refinement. Strain tensor results were obtained at these two points and averaged for onset predictions. Next, the strain tensor components were enhanced to account for micromechanical heterogeneity and combined to determine the strain invariants J_1 and J_2' . Given the axial strain applied to the test specimens of angles 10 to 67 degrees at failure, a plot of J_1 versus J_2' illustrated a unique onset surface that can be utilized for prediction of onset of irreversible behavior in a high performance carbon fiber composites with a glassy polymer matrix materials.

No effort was given to assessment of failure of the fiber phase in the present analysis and before this approach can be extended to the general multiaxial laminate wherein fiber failure is likely to be present, it will be necessary to make the appropriate extension in the micromechanical enhancement models. Further, the experiments carried out have focused on the onset of irreversible behavior in carbon fiber, glassy polymer composites wherein onset and failure are coincident; hence, the choice of the off-axis tensile test. However, onset is typically followed by propagation of damage and prediction of onset is clearly only the first

step in treating this more general problem. For design approaches where onset of irreversible behavior is the guiding design principle, the present approach should be adequate.

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